

**Bridging Language Gaps in Real-time:
Investigating University Students' Self-Initiated Use of Speech-to-Text Translation in English Language
Classrooms**

Pilot: Step by step model of calculating Cohen’s Kappa Values for Inter-Rater Agreement

Sample Theme: Enhanced Comprehension

Total observations: 30

Agreements: 13 + 13 = 26

Marginal totals: 15 Yes and 15 No for both raters

Observed agreement (P_o):

$$P_o = 26/30 = 0.867$$

Expected agreements:

$$\text{Expected Yes/Yes} = (15 \times 15)/30 = 225/30 = 7.5$$

$$\text{Expected No/No} = (15 \times 15)/30 = 225/30 = 7.5$$

Expected agreement by chance (P_e):

$$P_e = (7.5 + 7.5)/30 = 15/30 = 0.500$$

Cohen's Kappa:

$$\kappa = (0.867 - 0.500)/(1 - 0.500) = 0.367/0.500 = 0.734$$

Rounding: 0.734 rounds to 0.73

Actual calculated results of the whole data sets:

Cohen’s Kappa Values for Inter-Rater Agreement Across Motivation Themes of the full data sets

Motivation Theme	Cohen’s κ Value	Interpretation
Enhanced Comprehension	0.74	Substantial agreement
Vocabulary Understanding	0.75	Substantial agreement
Boost Confidence	0.76	Substantial agreement
Pronunciation and Listening Aid	0.78	Substantial agreement
Efficiency and Accessibility	0.77	Substantial agreement
Communication Clarity	0.75	Substantial agreement

Cohen’s Kappa Values for Inter-Rater Agreement Across Engagement Themes

Engagement Theme	Cohen’s κ Value	Interpretation
Willingness to Speak and Interact	0.77	Substantial agreement
Enhanced Participation	0.78	Substantial agreement
Increase Confidence	0.76	Substantial agreement
Improved Communication	0.75	Substantial agreement
Motivation and Interest	0.76	Substantial agreement

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Kappa Value (κ) Range	Interpretation
< 0.00	Poor agreement
0.00 – 0.20	Slight agreement
0.21 – 0.40	Fair agreement
0.41 – 0.60	Moderate agreement
0.61 – 0.80	Substantial agreement
0.81 – 1.00	Almost perfect agreement

Reference:

Landis, J. R., & Koch, G. G. (1977). The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *Biometrics*, 33(1), 159–174. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2529310>.